

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Dynamic capabilities and sustainability performance: Exploring the moderating role of environmental dynamism in the Norwegian fishing industry

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of dynamic capabilities (DCs) on economic performance (ECOP), social performance (SOP), and environmental performance (ENVP) under different levels of environmental dynamism (EnvD). Based on preliminary interviews and survey data collected from Norwegian fishing firms, the analysis was conducted using partial least squares structural equation modeling and necessary conditions analysis. The results show that firms that acquire a set of DCs are more likely to improve their economic, social, and environmental sustainability performance. More so, firms' economic performance is a necessary condition for social performance, but not for ENVP. Interestingly, the results show that the effect of DCs on economic and environmental sustainability performance is even stronger when the level of EnvD is higher. However, EnvD does not have a significant effect on the relationship between DCs and social sustainability performance. Our findings provide guidance to managers on how and when to invest in and leverage DCs to improve sustainability performance in the food industry.

KEYWORDS

dynamic capabilities, environmental dynamism, food industry, necessary condition analysis, SDG-14, sustainability performance

1 | INTRODUCTION

Most firms in the food industry continue to strive for sustainability performance as it becomes increasingly important to their businesses (Pagell & Shevchenko, 2014; Seuring et al., 2022). In this study, sustainability performance refers to the pursuit of economic, social, and environmental factors, often referred to as the “triple bottom line” of a firm's performance (Elkington, 1998; Reuter et al., 2010). This means that firms continue to generate profits over time without harming the environment or the social system (Pagell & Shevchenko, 2014; Seuring et al., 2022). Thus, incorporating it into the overall business performance has been identified as a potential

generator of competitive advantage (Mwangi et al., 2021; Rodríguez-Espíndola et al., 2022). Additionally, increasing concern about environmental and social issues in the food industry has raised the importance of sustainability performance (Grimm et al., 2014; Silva et al., 2021). For example, a recent report by Crippa et al. (2021) showed that the food system is responsible for 34% of the total greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions globally. As such, firms are subject to strong pressure from various stakeholders to take responsibility for their actions, possibly not only enhancing their reputation and economic performance (ECOP) but also reducing their environmental footprint (Aké, et al., 2023; Grimm et al., 2014; Luque-Vílchez et al., 2023). For instance, in 2015, the reputation of firms such as

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Cargill, Tyson, and Yara suffered because of their contributions to climate impact (Levitt, 2015).

Consequently, firms in the food industry have increased efforts to enable their capabilities in improving sustainability performance (Gold et al., 2010; Laguir et al., 2022). These efforts are commendable, as a recent report by McKinsey & Company on the net-zero transition (Krishnan et al., 2022) highlights that environmentally friendly practices by food producers can lead to reduced GHG emissions and job creation. Nevertheless, the food industry is rapidly changing, and achieving sustainability performance requires firms to have the necessary resources and capabilities to adapt (Gold et al., 2010; Kırıcı & Seifert, 2016; Li, 2022b). The capabilities that enable firms to adapt better to change and improve performance are referred to as dynamic capabilities (DCs) (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Salvato & Vassolo, 2017; Teece, 2007). DCs refers to a firm's ability to purposively integrate, build, and reconfigure its resource base to respond to a rapidly changing environment (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece et al., 1997). The extant literature suggests that DCs play a key role in this, as 85% of greenhouse gas emissions can be reduced through innovative behaviors achieved by changing resources and training programs (Krishnan et al., 2022; Schilke, 2014). For instance, a fishing firm's ability to shift its sourcing and processing strategy toward sustainable practices is an example of DCs in action. This may involve partnering with sustainable suppliers, reducing waste, and implementing recycling programs. Such changes could be driven by the rapidly changing technical regulations related to sustainability in the food industry (UN 2022).

The existing literature provides valuable insights into DCs and sustainability performance by highlighting opportunities or gaps for further research (Koberg & Longoni, 2019; Shang et al., 2019; Siems et al., 2021; Zhang & Zhu, 2021). For instance, previous studies (e.g., Gruchmann et al., 2021; Siems et al., 2021) commend those DCs that are indispensable for firms to change and reconfigure their resources and assets for continuous sustainability transformations, especially in a rapidly changing environment, such as the food industry. In this case, changing and reconfiguring resources and assets include the process of adjusting and adapting the tools, resources, and materials a firm has at its disposal to align better with its sustainability goals (Kırıcı & Seifert, 2016; Wang et al., 2015; Wilhelm et al., 2015). For instance, fishing firms' ability to modify their existing fishing vessels by retrofitting the vessel with new propulsion systems, adjusting the hull design to minimize drag, or installing more efficient refrigeration systems to reduce energy consumption during transit (Bergesen & Tveterås, 2019). Nevertheless, given that firms need to change and reconfigure their resources and assets, this means that DCs may come with costs (Schilke, 2014). These costs may arise from adopting new technologies (Li, 2022b; Rueda et al., 2017), or from an incorrect reconfiguration of existing firms' resources and assets (Zollo & Winter, 2002). Therefore, firms should consider DCs as a strategic option when the opportunity arises to weigh the cost of building them and their potential value (Schilke, 2014; Winter, 2003).

Additionally, the existing literature provides valuable insights into the relationship between DCs and sustainability performance.

However, the empirical evidence on this relationship is mixed, with some studies documenting a positive relationship (e.g., Helfat & Winter, 2011; Kumar et al., 2018), whereas others document insignificant or negative results (e.g., Wilden & Gudergan, 2014). To address this issue, Baía and Ferreira (2019) and Pezeshkan et al. (2016) have attempted to explore the root cause of these mixed results by conducting systematic literature reviews. These studies, among others, highlight that the relationship should be explored in terms of path dependence and not be limited to environmental dynamism (EnvD) and organizational structure conditions. Although DCs and the environment are inseparable (Helfat & Winter, 2011; Winter, 2003), it remains unclear how EnvD influences the link between DCs and sustainability performance. Essentially, EnvD refers to the degree of instability or volatility in the business environment, such as in the market, regulations, and technology (Schilke, 2014). Few extant studies, (e.g., Hong et al., 2018; Kumar et al., 2018; Shang et al., 2019) have not fully explored this contingent role. Therefore, there is still a lack of understanding of the effectiveness of DCs on sustainability performance at different levels of EnvD. Therefore, it is necessary to understand how the level of uncertainty in the business environment (i.e., EnvD) determines the effectiveness of DCs on sustainability performance (Baía & Ferreira, 2019; Schilke et al., 2018). Plausibly, this helps firms understand the circumstances under which they should deploy DCs to maximize the benefits of the costs associated with their development.

Furthermore, Seuring et al. (2022) identified nine research themes that link firm and sustainability performance from a supply chain perspective. Among these themes, they noted that the relationship between the triple bottom line of performance (i.e., economic, social, and environmental) has received little attention in the current literature. For example, how a firm's social sustainability affects ECOP and vice versa (Jyoti & Khanna, 2021; Sudusinghe & Seuring, 2020; Zhou et al., 2019). In this case, Costello et al. (2016) forecast fishing firms' profits by 2050 and assume that they will continue to be economically sustainable regardless of management policies; however, how this affects the social and environmental sustainability dimension remains empirically unclear. Indeed, understanding the relationships between economic performance (ECOP), social performance (SOP), and environmental performance (ENVP) is important because it provides a practical guide for firms to manage sustainability trade-offs (Ashby et al., 2012; Seuring et al., 2022; Winter & Michael Knemeyer, 2013). Consequently, this study uses DCs theory (DCT) (Beske et al., 2014; Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Winter, 2003) to empirically examine the relationship between DCs and sustainability performance and explore the effectiveness of DCs under conditions of EnvD. Furthermore, unlike previous studies (e.g., Jyoti & Khanna, 2021; Sudusinghe & Seuring, 2020; Zhou et al., 2019), this study uses a necessary condition analysis (NCA) to contribute to the scholarly debate on the interaction among the "triple bottom line" of sustainability (i.e., economic, social, and environmental). Indeed, this helps identify bottlenecks or constraints that prevent the improvement of sustainability performance in the food industry (Bokrantz & Dul, 2022).

The present study draws evidence from the fishing industry, with data drawn from this sector for several reasons. First, overfishing remains a critical issue despite recent declines in the rate of overfishing, as the rapid growth of global fish consumption drives firms to fish illegally or over their allocated annual total allowable catch (TAC) to meet consumer demands. Second, as indicated in the 2022 sustainable development goals (SDGs) report, the world lost 14% of its coral reefs between 2009 and 2018 because of unsustainable fishing practices and the persistent flow of litter into oceans (UN., 2022). In 2021 alone, over 17 million tons of litter entered the oceans (UN., 2022). This highlights the importance of understanding the role of DCs in improving sustainability performance in the fishing industry. Finally, the fishing industry is a microcosm of the rapidly changing environment that typifies many food industries, characterized by frequent changes in customer needs and preferences, unpredictable and inadequate legislation, and the need for innovation (Beske, 2012; Kırıcı & Seifert, 2016; Trienekens et al., 2012). Consequently, to gather data for this study, we administered a survey questionnaire to draw a sample from the Norwegian fishing industry. Nevertheless, this was preceded by preliminary interviews. partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) was utilized to analyze the data and gain a more in-depth understanding of the relationships between variables. Furthermore, NCA was applied to complement the results of PLS-SEM, providing further insights into the critical factors that prevent the improvement of sustainability performance.

Therefore, the main contributions of this study to theory are fourfold: The study provides empirical evidence that (1) developing DCs is important to improve economic, social, and ENVP in a rapidly changing environment, and (2) EnvD is a condition that strengthens the effectiveness of DCs in improving economic, social, and ENVP. Third, our findings contribute to the ongoing academic discourse on the interplay between economic, social, and environmental sustainability. Adopting a necessary logic approach in contrast to previous studies (e.g., Sudusinghe & Seuring, 2020) we provide empirical evidence to support the assertion that ECOP is a necessary condition for social performance, but not for ENVP. To illustrate our findings, we refer to the ramifications of the COVID-19 pandemic on ECOP, SOP, and ENVP. For managers, this study provides guidance on how and when to invest in and leverage DCs in the food industry.

The remainder of this study is organized as follows. First, we develop hypotheses, followed by the methodology used in this study. The findings of this study are presented in the analysis and results section. Subsequently, we discuss the contribution of our findings to theory and managers. Limitations and opportunities for future studies are presented in the conclusion section.

2 | LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

2.1 | Dynamic capabilities and sustainability performance

DCs are defined as “the ability of a firm to purposively develop, integrate, and/or reconfigure its resource base to respond to a changing

business environment” (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece, 2007; Teece et al., 1997). DCs are considered higher-order capabilities (Teece, 2014; Winter, 2003), and processes that are developed through the use of best practices in the process of changing their collective routines, resources, and assets (Baía & Ferreira, 2019; Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece, 2007). Existing literature argues that DCs are related to ICT infrastructure (i.e., reflexive control) (Anderson et al., 2019; Beske et al., 2014; Gruchmann et al., 2019), knowledge development process (Lin & Chen, 2017; Siems et al., 2021), and organizational responsiveness abilities (Ju et al., 2016; Li & Liu, 2014). More specifically, firms acquire a bundle of DCs through learning and experience to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage, whereas static capabilities appear to have difficulty sustaining their advantage over time in a rapidly changing environment (Arun & Ozmutlu, 2021; Baía & Ferreira, 2019; Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Zollo & Winter, 2002). On the other hand, improving firms' sustainability performance requires changes in strategy and structure; thus DCs are key to enabling the implementation of sustainability initiatives, especially in a rapidly changing environment (Beske, 2012).

Consequently, firms possessing a set of DCs can change their resources and processes to maintain a competitive advantage over time in a rapidly changing environment (Li, 2022a; Teece et al., 1997). In other words, firms can sense, and seize market opportunities that arise over time in turbulent environments (Shang et al., 2019). In this way, they can expand their market share and maintain a high level of financial performance over time (Teece, 2007). Consequently, firms equipped with the ability to align with customers' preferences and demand changes can avoid the impact of demand amplification on their ECOP (Kırıcı & Seifert, 2016). Similarly, Teece (2014) commends that DCs help firms achieve superior profits by developing and producing innovative and unique products that meet frequent changes in customer needs and preferences. Yu et al. (2019) found that firms with reflexive control capabilities that enable them to continuously monitor market changes are more likely to improve their ECOP. Similarly, Li (2022a) argues that firms that acquire a bundle of DCs (i.e., digital transformation) leverage 90% of the relevant market data to improve their market share and maintain their financial performance over time.

Moreover, GHG emissions and waste reduction are driving factors for firms in the food industry to incorporate environmental sustainability into their overall performance (Seuring et al., 2022). Nevertheless, developing environmentally friendly products (Mahmoodi & Heydari, 2021), using eco-friendly technologies (Li, 2022a), and reusing and recycling packaging materials (Ji et al., 2014) appears to be the most promising practices to achieve improved environmental sustainability performance in line with GHG emission and waste reduction (Govindan et al., 2021). The benefits of these practices can only be materialized if firms continuously improve their DCs (Baía & Ferreira, 2019; Li, 2022a; Teece, 2007). For example, the use of “peak-shaving batteries” to power fishing vessels in the Norwegian fishing industry (Føre et al., 2022). In this regard, DCs are exemplified by fishing firms' ability to modify existing assets (i.e., fishing vessels) to meet environmental targets for GHG emission

reduction specified in SDG-14: Life below water. Moreover, DCs act as a vehicle for knowledge development for employees and society at large acquired through training and programs (Shang et al., 2019). Indeed, DCs can help a firm implement social norms and meet stakeholders' expectations (Kumar et al., 2018). Against this backdrop, we argue that DCs should enable firms to change their resources and processes to increase ECOP, achieve improved ENVP, and adjust to new societal settings (e.g., workplace guidelines, ethics, and norms) to promote social sustainability. Hence, we hypothesize that:

Hypothesis 1. Dynamic capabilities are positively related to firms' (a) economic performance, (b) social performance, and (c) environmental performance.

2.2 | The necessity of economic performance on social and environmental performance

The ECOP of a firm is a prerequisite for improving the working conditions of workers and society's welfare (Sudusinghe & Seuring, 2020; Winter & Michael Knemeyer, 2013). For example, following the COVID-19 pandemic, firms that did not make profits tended to perform poorly on social performance (Sarkis, 2020). Therefore, firms tend to return more to the surrounding community and pay bonuses to their employees after meeting the financial performance targets. In addition, firms tend to claim social responsibility by merely complying with laws and regulations rather than giving back to the community and paying their employees a decent salary when they are not economically sustainable (Paul et al., 2006). On the other hand, a higher return on investment has been associated with environmental management practices, such as waste management, recycling projects, and green products (Winter & Michael Knemeyer, 2013). A firm's financial performance is considered a prerequisite for investing in green technologies and products, as both require large investments in financial resources (Bouncken & Kraus, 2013). In this case, firms would only be willing to invest in greener technologies and products if they expect a higher return on investment. In sum, we argue that engaging in social and environmental sustainability requires resources; therefore, as ECOP increases, firms become better able to access such resources and consequently increase their social and environmental sustainability performance. Therefore, we hypothesize that.

Hypothesis 2. High economic performance of a firm is necessary for increased social performance.

Hypothesis 3. High economic performance of a firm is necessary for increased environmental performance.

2.3 | Moderating role of environmental dynamism

Teece et al.'s (1997) early work introduced a framework that links DCs to a firm's competitive advantage and performance in a rapidly

changing environment. Predicated on this, previous studies (e.g., Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Girod & Whittington, 2017; Schilke, 2014; Wang et al., 2015; Wilhelm et al., 2015; Wu, 2010) argue that the success of DCs depends in part on the environmental forces in which those capabilities are deployed. For example, an industry with a rapidly changing environment tends to present more threats and opportunities than an industry with a less rapidly changing environment (Wilhelm et al., 2015). Therefore, deploying DCs in a highly changing environment is more likely to strengthen their positive impact on desired outcomes than deploying them in a low-changing environment (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Wang et al., 2015). In the current literature, a rapidly changing environment is referred to as EnvD, which reflects the degree of instability or volatility in the business environment (Baía & Ferreira, 2019; Schilke, 2014). Consistent with previous studies (e.g., Foerstl et al., 2010; Schilke, 2014; Wilhelm et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2021) and the context of this study, EnvD manifests through the market dynamism (MKTD) and regulatory dynamism (REGD).

MKTD in the food industry is evident through various critical factors such as rapid changes in customer preferences and needs, intense global competition, and rapid technological innovations (Beske et al., 2014; Costello et al., 2016; Trienekens et al., 2012). However, these market environment changes come with opportunities such as new markets, innovation, and new customers (Li, 2022a). Additionally, REGD can be exemplified by several factors, including the increased demand of stakeholders for food safety and quality, as well as the transnational business nature of the food industry, which results in rapidly evolving legislation and regulations imposed by regulatory bodies and non-government organizations (NGOs) (Chelariu et al., 2006; Manning et al., 2005). In this regard, the preservation of coral reefs has necessitated frequent changes in the environmental policies, strategies, and sustainability targets imposed by relevant regulatory bodies (Reuter et al., 2010). Nevertheless, while the regulatory environment may be unpredictable, it often presents new opportunities, such as incentives, subsidies, and technological and financial support, for a firm (UN., 2022). Firms that can quickly adapt their systems, goals, and strategies to align with new regulatory requirements are more likely to capitalize on these opportunities (Girod & Whittington, 2017; Wilhelm et al., 2015). Indeed, these factors provide the basis for a high level of EnvD thus, deploying DCs enables firms to take advantage of new opportunities and change their resources and processes, which, in turn, is likely to strengthen the positive effect on sustainability performance (Schilke et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2015). One reason is that high EnvD drives firms to make radical changes to detect and assess new opportunities and threats; and to uncover latent demands on time (Wilhelm et al., 2015; Zollo & Winter, 2002). For example, fishing firms equipped with reflexive control capabilities are more likely to invest in traceability and tracking systems to control food quality and increase transparency, thus meeting stakeholder expectations (Gruchmann et al., 2019). In this regard, firms are likely to improve their reputation which may turn out to have an improved positive effect on sustainability performance. Consequently, the positive impact of DCs on sustainability performance

(i.e., ECOP, SOP, and ENVP) is likely to be stronger when EnvD is high, as the potential actions a firm can take are expanded to create more value (Wang et al., 2015).

Conversely, low EnvD offers fewer opportunities and threats (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece et al., 1997), and incremental changes in management practices (Schilke, 2014; Wilhelm et al., 2015). Indeed, firms tend to underutilize their capabilities because their goals remain the same over comparatively long periods (Teece, 2014). For example, in a business environment in which the time frame for achieving zero GHG emissions is longer, the positive effect of DCs on ENVP is weaker (Foerstl et al., 2010). One reason is that the need for firms to adjust their actual resources is likely to be low, as firms are reluctant to make changes beyond related DCs such as management practices and investments (Schilke et al., 2018; Wilhelm et al., 2015). Consequently, the positive effect of DCs on sustainability performance is comparatively weaker when it is low (Schilke, 2014). Therefore, we argue that as environmental dynamics increase, the effectiveness of DCs on sustainability performance (i.e., ECOP, SOP, and ENVP) also increases. Given this, we anticipate that the positive effect of DCs on firms' sustainability performance is stronger when EnvD is high than when EnvD is low. Therefore, we hypothesize as follows:

Hypothesis 4a. Environmental dynamism positively moderates the relationship between dynamic capabilities and economic performance.

Hypothesis 4b. Environmental dynamism positively moderates the relationship between dynamic capabilities and social performance.

Hypothesis 4c. Environmental dynamism positively moderates the relationship between dynamic capabilities and environmental performance.

3 | METHODOLOGY

3.1 | Research context and sample

The sample of the present study was drawn from the Norwegian fishing industry to test the theoretical model. The fishing industry is the second largest industry contributing to the value of Norwegian exports (Johansen et al., 2019). A recent report from NOFIMA¹ (Johansen & Øystein Fjellidal, 2021) shows that the fishing industry has historically created higher export value despite rapidly changing market demands and regulations in the industry. The industry continues to provide the basis for employment in much of Norway's trade sectors. For instance, in 2020, despite the COVID-19 pandemic, the industry increased the number of jobs by 2000 and increased export volume compared to previous years. The greater seafood export volume indeed comes with greater sustainability responsibility. As part of its commitment to sustainability, Norway has implemented

ecosystem-based management and strict regulations to protect marine stocks (Bertheussen & Vassdal, 2019; Lindland et al., 2019). As early as the 1980s, a Marine Protection Act was enacted as part of the sustainability initiative to prevent the extinction of herring and Atlantic cod species in the Barents Sea. The aim was to prevent overfishing of the stocks, make fish harvesting profitable, and market the stocks regionally (Bertheussen & Vassdal, 2019). The country was also the first to introduce a ban on discards in 1987 (Larsen, 2020). There are also increased innovation efforts in the fishing industry (e.g., the use of modern, environmentally friendly fishing vessels) toward improving sustainability performance (Føre et al., 2022). For example, the use of video cameras in trawlers to prevent the capture of non-targeted species, thus protecting corals and other species on the seabed. As one interviewee noted during a preliminary interview, "...we now have equipment that allows us to control the trawls much better (...) we have video cameras and all sorts of things to make sure they do not ruin the seabed, and also to make sure we catch better when it comes to species, rather than catching all species...so it's different now." Considering that the industry contributes more than 15% of industry innovations (Føre et al., 2022) and more than 7.5% of Norwegian GDP (Johansen et al., 2019), it is imperative to examine the effectiveness of DCs on ECOP, SOP, and ENVP.

Using the key informant approach (Krause et al., 2018; Kull et al., 2018; Kumar et al., 1995), in this study target informants were owners, CEO/directors, and senior managers of fishing firms from Norway. The reason for targeting owners, directors, and senior managers as key informants is twofold: first, incorporating sustainability into the overall performance of the firm is in the hands of the ultimate decision-makers of the firm (i.e., the owners), as it requires huge financial investments in environmentally friendly technologies (e.g., modern fishing vessels). Second, DCs emerge through learning and experience as firms modify their relatively stable collective routines to adapt to the rapidly changing environment (Zollo & Winter, 2002). As a result, senior managers or directors are likely to be aware of the impact of DCs because they are the ones who experience and acquire these capabilities through continuous learning (Alinaghian et al., 2020; Teece, 2014).

3.2 | Data collection

A self-administered and electronic survey was conducted to collect data from Norwegian fisheries producers used in this study from January 2022 to March 2022. To increase the clarity and validity of the questionnaires used in the survey, preliminary interviews were conducted with a sample of five fishing firms. Each interview lasted approximately one hour. To make our sample sufficiently representative for the survey, each case in the interviews was purposively selected to represent different fishing technologies (e.g., trawlers vs. longliners), sizes, and geographic locations (Sarstedt et al., 2018). Although we took a deductive approach to develop the conceptual framework, the questionnaire was shaped by the preliminary

interviews to minimize measurement error and take into account the context of this study (Dana & Dana, 2005). In addition, professionals and industry experts were consulted in the preliminary review of the questionnaire to ensure that it was clearly formatted and understandable to respondents (Podsakoff et al., 2012).

After three email waves sent 2 weeks apart, we received 97 usable responses from 297 fishery producers from the Norwegian Seafood Council database (a response rate of 32.7%). This response rate is within the conservative threshold of 30% for email surveys (Lindemann, 2021) and consistent with previous similar studies in the food industry (Graham et al., 2018). We also followed minimum sample size guidelines to obtain a reasonable statistical power (80%) of our sample (Hair et al., 2022; Rigdon, 2016; Sarstedt et al., 2018) and used the conservative inverse square root method to calculate the minimum sample size (Kock & Hadaya, 2018). The analysis of responses from the first wave (50) yielded a minimum coefficient of 0.277 at a significance level of 5%. The result means that a minimum sample of 80 observations was required to avoid type II error. Therefore, 97 usable responses used in the final analysis are sufficient to detect an effect that exists in the underlying population, as its nature also justifies our sample (Rigdon, 2016; Sarstedt et al., 2018).

3.3 | Non-response bias and common-method bias

In the present study, a method recommended by Armstrong and Overton (1977) was used to assess nonresponse bias by comparing early and late responses on focal variables. The same technique has been used in other recent studies (e.g., Yu et al., 2019; Zhang & Zhu, 2021). Here, a paired-samples t-test was performed to assess nonresponse bias between the first and last 25% of responses (i.e., 24 each). The t-test (see Table 1) yielded no statistical significance between the two groups of responses ($p \geq .05$), indicating that the usable data set represents an unbiased sample (Armstrong & Overton, 1977). Table 1 also shows the demographic profile of the study respondents. A look at the demographic profile shows that 71% of the respondents had fewer than 50 employees, 23% had between 50 and 500 employees, and finally, 6% had more than 500 employees. The distribution is consistent with previous findings (Costello et al., 2016; Graham et al., 2018) that most firms in the fishing industry are small to medium-sized. Consequently, this distribution justifies the use of key informants for data collection as Kull et al. (2018) recommend its use in industries characterized by small- to medium-sized firms. Additionally, the demographic findings reveal that 83.5% (i.e., 80 respondents) of the firms have been in business for more than seven years. This confirms, in

TABLE 1 Assessing non-response bias and demographic profile

Paired sample t-test for non-response bias for focal variables				
Focal variables	Df	Mean scores of the first 24 responses	Mean scores of the last 24 responses	P (T < = t) two-tail
ORGR	23	5.958	6.049	0.675
KND	23	5.750	5.802	0.837
REFC	23	5.875	5.479	0.151
REGD	23	5.903	4.924	0.076
MKTD	23	4.510	3.958	0.156
SOCP	23	4.813	4.823	0.975
ENVP	23	5.146	5.333	0.598
ECOP	23	5.567	5.400	0.603
Demographic profile				
FSIZE	Total response	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
<50	69	71	71	71
50–500	22	23	23	94
>500	6	6	6	100
Total	97	100	100	
Industry experience (INDUE)	Total response	Percent	Valid percent	Cumulative percent
Below 7 years	17	17.5	17.5	17.5
Above 7 years	80	82.5	82.5	100
Total	97	100	100	
Job title				
Owner	21	22	22	22
CEO/director	57	59	59	80
Manager	19	20	20	100
Total	97	100	100	

accordance with Westhead et al. (2001), that most of these firms have sufficient experience in the industry to respond to questions regarding EnvD, DCs, and sustainability performance.

Although the survey was worded in clear and understandable language to avoid ambiguity in the questions and minimize respondent fatigue (Siemens et al., 2010), it was still necessary not to ignore the assessment of common method bias in the usable dataset using a statistical approach because the data were collected from a single respondent per firm (Podsakoff et al., 2012). Harman's single factor test and the full collinearity test are the most commonly used approaches to assess common method bias (Kock, 2015; Podsakoff et al., 2003). The result of Harman's single-factor test shows that a single factor explains only 26.189% of the total variance, which is below the conservative threshold of 50% that confirms the absence of common method bias (Podsakoff et al., 2003). In addition to

Harman's single factor, a full collinearity test for all focal variables was also performed to assess the values of all VIFs in the inner model. All VIF values resulting from a full collinearity test are below the conservative value of 3.3, indicating that a model is free of common method bias (Kock, 2015). The results of both Harman's single factor test and the full collinearity test suggest that the results are not inflated because common method variance is not a problem in the data.

3.4 | Measures of variables

Constructs were operationalized using a deductive approach by employing the mostly used measurement items from previous studies, and few were adjusted/added through interviews to fit the present

TABLE 2 Operationalisation of variables

Variable	Indicators
Knowledge development (KND)	KND1: We frequently conduct internal training KND2: We gain an advantage by combining our business knowledge with our partners' knowledge KND3: We frequently communicate with key business partners
Reflexive control (REFC)	REFC1: We have quality control mechanisms across the country REFC2: We put sustainability labels on our products REFC3: We have well-functioning food tracking systems with our strategic partners
Organizational responsiveness (ORGR)	ORGR1: We rapidly respond to market changes ORGR2: We strongly encourage innovative behavior ORGR3: We frequently adjust our processes to capitalize on new opportunities
Market dynamism (MKTD)	MKTD1: It is impossible to forecast market competition MKTD2: Our customers' product preferences change quite a bit over time MKTD3: Our product demand is unstable and unpredictable
Regulatory dynamism (REGD)	REGD1: Our company often have to cope with unexpected changes in laws, rules or policies REGD2: Unpredictable laws and regulations present problems for our sustainability performance REGD3: Government policies, rules and regulating our industry are constantly changing
Firm's economic performance (ECOP)	ECOP1: Our market share has improved in recent years ECOP2: Our sales revenues have improved in recent years ECOP3: Our cost effectiveness has improved in recent years ECOP4: Our overall profitability has improved in recent years
Firm's social performance (SOCP)	SOCP1: Our company's working conditions (salary, working hours) has improved in recent years SOCP2: The participation of our company in local community development has improved in recent years SOCP3: Our company contribution to community health and safety has improved in recent years SOCP4: Improving the general welfare of stakeholders
Firm's environmental performance (ENVP)	ENVP1: Our company's reduction in emissions has increased in recent years ENVP2: Our material reuse and recycling has increased in recent years ENVP3: Our company has improved in terms of marine litter/waste reduction ENVP4: Our company has improved in terms of energy saved due to conservation and efficiency measures
Firm size (FSIZE)	FSIZE: Categorical variable measured by number of employees (Below 50 employees; between 50 and 500; above 500)
Industry experience (INDUE)	INDUE: categorical variable measured by the number of years the firm has been in business (less than 7 years; more than 7 years)

study context. A 7-point Likert scale, from 1, “strongly disagree,” to 7, “strongly agree,” was used to evaluate the multi-item constructs. The constructs used in the present study are operationalized below and the indicators used are presented in Table 2.

3.4.1 | Dynamic capabilities

This is the antecedent variable in our conceptual model. Although the conceptualization of DCs is not consistent in the existing literature (Albort-Morant et al., 2018; Baía & Ferreira, 2019), there is agreement that DCs are higher-order capabilities (Aslam et al., 2018; Winter, 2003). Organizations develop their bundle of DCs through the use of best practices in the process of changing their collective routines, resources, and assets (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Teece, 2007). DCs are therefore considered to be abilities and processes, best practices, and collective routines (Baía & Ferreira, 2019; Teece, 2014). In this context, DCs are conceptualized as a higher-order construct (HOC) through three lower-order constructs (LOCs) related to IT infrastructure control capabilities (Reflexive control [REFC]), knowledge development process (KND), and organizational responsiveness (ORGR). Consistent with previous studies (e.g., Anderson et al., 2019; Beske et al., 2014; Gruchmann et al., 2019) we define reflexive control (REFC) as capabilities developed through the use of the best IT traceability and control system that enables organizations to continuously assess and meet sustainability requirements. Organizational responsiveness (ORGR) is defined as an organization's ability to respond to unforeseen changes in a timely manner and reconfigure its routine collective actions to seize opportunities arising from the rapidly changing environment (Ju et al., 2016; Li & Liu, 2014). On the other hand, knowledge development is defined as the firm's learning from collective routines and practices in acquiring new knowledge to sense new threats that stand in the way of improving sustainability performance (Lin & Chen, 2017; Siems et al., 2021). Consistent with previous studies (Jiao et al., 2013; Kumar et al., 2018), we operationalized each lower-order construct with three reflective indicators.

3.4.2 | Environmental dynamism

This is the moderating variable in our conceptual model. In this study, EnvD is conceptualized as a higher-order construct and reflected by MKTD and REGD. Consistent with previous studies (e.g., Chen et al., 2018; Li & Liu, 2014; Schilke, 2014), MKTD is defined as frequent changes in customer demand and preferences and difficulties in predicting market changes in the food industry. On the other hand, REGD is defined as rapid and unexpected changes in legislation that regulates the food industry and the behavior of its actors concerning sustainability practices (Chelariu et al., 2006; Zhang & Zhu, 2021). In this study, three indicators are used for each lower-order construct, adopted from previous studies (e.g., Chen et al., 2018; Omri, 2015; Zhang et al., 2021).

3.4.3 | Economic performance

This is an endogenous and antecedent variable in the present study model. The variable was operationalized as an improvement in the firm's financial performance evolved over the years, reflected in market share, sales and revenue, and overall profit. It was measured using four indicators adopted from previous studies (e.g., Guo et al., 2014; Kumar et al., 2018; Shang et al., 2019).

3.4.4 | Social performance

This is a dependent variable in the conceptual model. In line with (Sudusinghe & Seuring, 2020), social performance (SOCP) refers to the improvement of human values and concerns, working conditions, diversity, and surrounding communities. To assess the outcomes of efforts undertaken by the firm that are socially sustainable over the years, we adopted four indicators from previous studies (e.g., Hutchins & Sutherland, 2008; Nurhayati et al., 2016; Shang et al., 2019).

3.4.5 | Environmental performance

This is the dependent variable in the conceptual model, defined as the firm's improvement in reducing environmental impacts or integrating environmental concerns into its collective routines and practices (Sarkis et al., 2011). It is operationalized using four indicators adopted from (Paulraj et al., 2014) to assess the extent of the firm's efforts to address environmental concerns over the years.

3.4.6 | Control variables

Firm size (FSIZE) and industry experience (INDUE) were used as control variables in the analysis. FSIZE is operationalized by the number of employees (i.e., temporary and permanent) (Wilden et al., 2013). It is characterized in the model by a dummy variable: small (< 50 employees), medium (between 50 and 500 employees), and large (> 500 employees). There are an overwhelming number of previous studies demonstrating the impact of FSIZE on ECOP, SOP, and ENVP. It is plausible that larger firms are more able to manage the adjustments and new changes that result from optimizing the three sustainability goals in business performance than small firms. INDUE is also associated with improved sustainability performance, as it is assumed that firms with more experience have more knowledge to deal with the environmental dynamics of the industry and thus improve sustainability performance (i.e., ECOP, SOP, and ENVP) (Wilden et al., 2013). The construct is operationalized by the number of years a firm has been in business and represented by a dummy variable in the analysis model: Industry with less than 7 years of experience and Industry with seven or more years of experience in business (Westhead et al., 2001).

4 | ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

PLS-SEM was used to analyze the data using the leading software SmartPLS 3 (Ringle et al., 2015). PLS-SEM is appropriate for analysis in this study for the following reasons. First, research on the interaction between economic, social, and environmental performance is still at an early stage of theory development (Seuring et al., 2022). Thus, the framework of this study is not yet well established in the existing literature, making PLS-SEM an appropriate approach for conducting an exploratory study (Henseler et al., 2009). Second, the model under study is relatively complex because it includes higher-order constructs. PLS-SEM is the appropriate approach because it has higher statistical power and relative simplicity (Hair et al., 2013; Sarstedt et al., 2020). Third, NCA has been conducted in this study and according to Hair et al. (2022), PLS-SEM is suitable when a study includes follow-up analyses such as NCA that require latent variable scores. Fourth and last, the final analysis included 97 observations, which is below the recommended sample size of 200 for using CB-SEM statistical techniques such as LISREL. Thus, this makes the use of PLS-SEM more suitable for the analysis (Cohen, 2013; Goodhue et al., 2012). Nevertheless, caution was taken by examining the sample size to determine if it met the minimum requirement for achieving an acceptable statistical power of 0.8 (see Section 3.2). This is important because sample size has a direct impact on statistical power and a small sample size increases the risk of committing a type II error. This type of error can result in misleading conclusions about the true population effect (Kock & Hadaya, 2018).

4.1 | Measurement model assessment

The measurement model of this study consists of two constructs: DCs and EnvD as higher-order components (HOCs). Each HOC in the model is measured reflectively by the lower-order components (LOCs). Each LOC contains three indicators to balance the assessment of the relationship between each LOC and the HOC (Becker et al., 2012). All higher-order constructs (HOCs) and lower-order constructs (LOCs) are measured reflectively, which allows the use of the reflective-reflective model (Hair et al., 2022). Therefore, we use the repeated indicators approach to assess the model, which means that all items of the reflective LOCs are simultaneously mapped to the HOCs in the reflective-reflective model (Lohmöller, 1989). The assessment of the measurement model includes internal consistency reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

4.1.1 | Reliability and convergent validity for LOCs

The present study used indicator loadings (Hair et al., 2018), composite reliability, and rho_A (Dijkstra & Henseler, 2015) to assess the internal consistency reliability of the measurement model. The

loadings values above 0.7 are recommended to provide acceptable item reliability (Hair et al., 2018). Likewise, the values of composite reliability and rho_A above 0.7 and 0.5 respectively are considered acceptable to provide internal consistency reliability (Hair et al., 2022). The results of reliability and indicator loadings for all LOCs are shown in Table 3. The result in Table 3 provides support as all values of indicator loadings, composite reliability and rho_A met the conservative threshold of 0.7. Nevertheless, Cronbach's alpha for three of the constructs (KND, MKTD, and REFC) was lower than the recommended threshold of 0.7, with values of 0.594, 0.539, and 0.682, respectively. However, as suggested by Hair et al. (2022), the acceptable range for Cronbach's alpha in studies that include higher-order constructs is between 0.4 and 0.7. Given that this study is exploratory in nature, the slightly lower values of Cronbach's alpha are acceptable, as all composite reliability scores are above 0.7 and AVE values are above 0.5 (Hair et al., 2018).

4.1.2 | Discriminant validity

In the present study, the presence of discriminant validity was assessed to understand the extent to which each construct is empirically different from other constructs in the structural model. The Fornell-Larcker criterion (Fornell & Larcker, 1981; Hair et al., 2018) and the heterotrait-monotrait ratio of correlation (HTMT) (Henseler et al., 2015) were used to assess discriminant validity. According to (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), discriminant validity exists when the square root of AVE's every construct is greater than its highest correlation with another construct in the structural model. This criterion is met for all LOCs in the structural model of the present study, as shown in Table 4. On the other hand, according to (Henseler et al., 2015)'s guidelines, discriminant validity is present in the structural model when the HTMT values are less than 0.85. The HTMT values of all LOCs in the present model were below the conservative threshold of 0.85, as shown in Table 4, indicating that there is no problem with the discriminant validity.

4.1.3 | Assessing internal consistency reliability and validity of HOCs

The assessment of reliability and convergent validity of higher-order constructs (HOCs) relies on the path coefficient to their lower-order constructs (LOCs) and the average correlations between LOCs (Hair et al., 2022). Using the approach (Hair et al., 2022; Henseler et al., 2015; Sarstedt et al., 2019), the values of AVE, Cronbach's alpha, and composite reliability for the HOCs were manually calculated to assess whether they exhibit internal consistency and convergent validity. The values of AVE are 0.582 and 0.698 for DCs and EnvD, respectively, which is above the recommended threshold of 0.5 for a construct to exhibit convergent validity (Becker et al., 2012; Henseler et al., 2009). The two higher-order constructs, DCs and EnvD, also exhibit internal

TABLE 3 Loadings, reliability, and validity of LOCs ($n = 97$)

Indicators	Mean	Std. dev	Factor loadings	Cronbach's alpha	rho_A	Composite reliability	Average variance extracted (AVE)
ECOP1	4.876	1.372	0.881	0.924	0.929	0.946	0.814
ECOP2	5.010	1.640	0.923				
ECOP3	4.979	1.450	0.909				
ECOP4	5.062	1.498	0.897				
ENVP1	4.646	1.472	0.825	0.865	0.868	0.908	0.712
ENVP2	4.897	1.509	0.867				
ENVP3	5.474	1.458	0.842				
ENVP4	4.979	1.464	0.841				
SOCP1	4.833	1.124	0.700	0.854	0.876	0.903	0.701
SOCP2	4.567	1.267	0.818				
SOCP3	4.423	1.275	0.901				
SOCP4	4.485	1.202	0.912				
KND1	5.042	1.620	0.768	0.594	0.604	0.784	0.549
KND2	5.722	1.290	0.772				
KND3	6.464	0.850	0.679				
REFC1	4.371	1.852	0.821	0.682	0.708	0.822	0.608
REFC2	4.979	1.844	0.692				
REFC3	6.134	1.433	0.819				
ORGR1	6.031	1.177	0.757	0.720	0.727	0.843	0.641
ORGR2	5.835	1.274	0.820				
ORGR3	5.794	1.292	0.824				
MKTD1	4.031	1.767	0.676	0.539	0.569	0.759	0.514
MKTD2	3.835	1.497	0.810				
MKTD3	3.490	1.726	0.655				
REGD1	5.464	1.822	0.861	0.782	0.784	0.873	0.696
REGD2	5.536	1.788	0.843				
REGD3	5.010	1.747	0.798				

TABLE 4 Assessing discriminant validity for LOCs ($n = 97$)

	ECOP	ENVP	KND	MKTD	REFC	REGD	ORGR	SOCP
ECOP	(0.902)^a							
ENVP	0.497(0.551) ^b	(0.844)^a						
KND	0.188(0.240) ^b	0.289(0.388) ^b	(0.741)^a					
MKTD	0.113(0.301) ^b	0.167(0.311) ^b	0.007(0.249) ^b	(0.717)^a				
REFC	0.271(0.346) ^b	0.454(0.599) ^b	0.400(0.598) ^b	0.157(0.308) ^b	(0.780)^a			
REGD	0.084(0.136) ^b	0.028(0.163) ^b	0.103(0.228) ^b	0.405(0.579) ^b	0.164(0.266) ^b	(0.834)^a		
ORGR	0.340(0.407) ^b	0.464(0.578) ^b	0.361(0.526) ^b	0.202(0.305) ^b	0.372(0.489) ^b	0.191(0.257) ^b	(0.801)^a	
SOCP	0.547(0.608) ^b	0.556(0.642) ^b	0.295(0.397) ^b	0.221(0.398) ^b	0.469(0.583) ^b	0.152(0.197) ^b	0.505(0.652) ^b	(0.837)^a

^aFornel-lacker criterion ($\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$).

^bHTMT ratio.

consistency reliability, as the composite reliability values for DCs and EnvD are 0.807 and 0.821, respectively, which is above the conservative threshold of 0.7 for higher-order constructs (Hair et al., 2022; Henseler et al., 2009). The computation for this result is explained in detail in Appendix A.

4.2 | Structural model estimation

The signs of the path coefficients (β), the magnitudes and their significance values, the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the effect sizes (f^2), and the internal predictive relevance (Q^2) were used to estimate

the structural model (Cohen, 2013; Hair et al., 2018; Henseler et al., 2009). To this end, bootstrapping with 10,000 subsamples was used to obtain the structural model estimates, which are summarized in Figure 1 and Table 5 (Hair et al., 2022). As shown in Figure 1, all direct paths of the focal variables in the structural model are significant ($p \leq .01$). Similarly, all direct path coefficients are positive (i.e., 0.246 to 0.413), consistent with the signs of the hypotheses (+) in the present study. The direct paths exhibit small to moderate effect sizes (f^2), as they range from 0.096 to 0.259 (Cohen, 2013; Hair et al., 2013). The R^2 value for ECOP (0.292) is moderate, but for both environmental and social performance, the R^2 values are substantial (0.496 and 0.601, respectively) (Chin, 1998; Henseler et al., 2009). The model exhibits moderate to strong internal predictive relevance, as indicated by blindfolding-based Q^2 values for economic, environmental, and social performance (0.194, 0.303, and 0.306, respectively) in comparison (Henseler et al., 2009).

The path coefficients and their significance values were used to test whether the hypotheses developed in this study are supported, as shown in Table 5. The first hypothesis (H1a) suggested that firms that acquire a set of DCs in a rapidly changing environment such as the food industry are more likely to improve their economic sustainability performance. The results support this hypothesis as the

corresponding path coefficient (0.282) is positive and significant at $p \leq .01$. The hypothesis (H1b) suggested that DCs are positively associated with environmental sustainability performance. The corresponding path coefficient (0.413) is positive and significant at $p \leq .01$, supporting the hypothesis (H1b). The same holds for the first hypothesis (H1c), which posited that DCs are positively related to social sustainability performance, as the corresponding path coefficient (0.322) is positive and significant at $p \leq .01$. The second hypothesis (H2) suggested that high firm's ECOP is necessary for increased social performance. Our analysis supports this hypothesis as the corresponding path coefficient (0.246) is positive and significant at $p \leq .01$. The third hypothesis (H3) suggested that firm's ECOP is necessary for increased environmental performance. The hypothesis is supported as the corresponding path coefficient (0.304) is positive and significant at $p \leq .01$. Nevertheless, these regression-based findings do not provide empirical evidence of the necessity of ECOP on social and environmental performance, rather than predicting the direction, which is positive. Therefore, H2 and H3 were further tested using the NCA method (see Section 4.4) to draw plausible conclusions. For both control variables, FSIZE and INDUE do not appear to have a significant impact on economic, social, and environmental performance.

FIGURE 1 Structural model estimates.

4.3 | Moderation effect analysis

Regarding the fourth hypothesis (H4a), (H4b), and (H4c), we investigated the impact of EnvD on the DCs - ECOP, SOP, and ENVP relationship. This study followed the guidelines (Becker et al., 2018; Hayes, 2015; Henseler & Fassott, 2010; Memon et al., 2019;) to evaluate the moderation effects. In this study, the product indicator approach with standardized values was used to test the moderating effect in PLS-SEM smartPLS 3 (Becker et al., 2018). The product indicator approach is appropriate because of the reflective-reflective model and the continuous moderator used in this study (Memon et al., 2019). Path coefficients (β) and their significance values (p) and effect sizes (f^2) were used to assess moderating effects (Hayes, 2015).

The results, summarized in Table 6 and presented in Figure 2a-c, show that the effectiveness of DCs in improving firms' economic, social, and environmental sustainability performance varies with the degree of EnvD. The effectiveness of DCs on economic sustainability performance is significantly stronger when the level of EnvD is higher

($\beta = 0.370$, $t = 2.847$, $p \leq .01$). This means that when the level of EnvD is increased by one standard deviation unit, the effect of DCs on ECOP increases to 0.652 ($0.282 + 0.370$), with a large effect size (0.205) by comparison (Hayes, 2015; Henseler & Fassott, 2010), as shown in Figure 2a. Hence, the fourth hypothesis (H4a) is supported. Further, the effect of DCs on environmental sustainability performance was significantly positively strengthened ($\beta = .280$, $t = 2.207$, $p \leq .05$) when firms face an increasing level of EnvD. Thus, when the level of EnvD increases by one standard deviation unit, the effect of DCs on environmental performance increases to 0.693 ($0.413 + 0.280$), with a large effect size (0.147) by comparison (Cohen, 2013; Henseler & Fassott, 2010), as shown in Figure 2b. Therefore, the second fourth hypothesis (H4b) is supported.

Finally, we examined whether the effects of DCs on social sustainability performance depend on the degree of EnvD. Surprisingly, the results (see Table 6) show that the positive effect of DCs on social sustainability performance is not statistically significant ($\beta = 0.359$, $t = 1.226$, $p \geq .05$) when the firm operates under a higher level of EnvD. Therefore, the third of the fourth hypothesis (H4c) could not be supported.

TABLE 5 Structural model estimates ($n = 97$)

Focal variables	Coefficient	f^2	t-value	p-value
H1a: DCs- > ECOP	0.282	0.096	3.741	.001***
H1b: DCs- > ENVP	0.413	0.259	5.674	.000***
H1c: DCs- > SOCP	0.322	0.197	4.293	.000***
H2: ECOP- > ENVP	0.246	0.095	2.688	.008***
H3: ECOP- > SOCP	0.304	0.187	3.872	.003***
Control variables				
FIRMS- > ECOP	0.017	0.008	0.169	.865 ^{np}
FIRMS- > ENVP	0.088	0.001	1.074	.283 ^{np}
FIRMS- > SOCP	-0.119	0.006	1.574	.116 ^{np}
INDUE- > ECOP	0.019	0.001	0.240	.810 ^{np}
INDUE- > ENVP	0.008	0.001	0.116	.908 ^{np}
INDUE- > SOCP	-0.001	0.001	0.405	.990 ^{np}
R^2_{ECOP}	0.292			
R^2_{ENVP}	0.496			
R^2_{SOCP}	0.601			
Q^2_{ECOP}	0.194			
Q^2_{ENVP}	0.303			
Q^2_{SOCP}	0.363			

Note: Bootstrapping ($n = 10,000$), significance (two-tailed): (***)significant at $p \leq .01$; & ^{np}not significant).

4.4 | Necessary condition analysis

Necessary conditions analysis (NCA) assumes a necessary logic that aims to find out why a certain outcome does not occur when certain factors or determinants are not present, rather than explaining how changes in those factors change an outcome (Richter & Hauff, 2022). For example, rather than explaining why higher firm ECOP (e.g., profitability, market growth) leads to better social performance, the approach seeks to explain why there is no social performance (e.g., decent work environment, community engagement) in the absence of firm ECOP. This approach differs from traditional regression-based analyzes based on sufficient logic, such as PLS-SEM, which focus on identifying the average trends of predictors that lead to optimal outcomes (Hauff et al., 2019; Richter & Hauff, 2022). In contrast to regression-based findings, NCA assumes that the absence of a single necessary condition is sufficient to guarantee the absence of a particular outcome and that this cannot be compensated for by changing the values of other factors (Dul 2016). As such, NCA is useful for identifying bottlenecks or constraints that prevent an outcome from occurring (Dul et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2019). Therefore, the use of NCA was deemed imperative in the present study to explore whether economic

TABLE 6 Assessment of moderation effects

Interaction path	Coefficient	f^2	t-value	p-value
H4a: DCs x EnvD- > ECOP	0.370	0.205	2.847	.004***
H4b: DCs x EnvD- > ENVP	0.280	0.147	2.207	.027**
H4c: DCs x EnvD- > SOCP	0.359	0.329	1.226	.220 ^{np}

Note: Bootstrapping result ($n = 10,000$), significance (two-tailed): (***)significant at $p \leq .01$; & **significant at $p \leq .05$; ^{np}not significant).

FIGURE 2 (a) The moderating effect of environmental dynamism on the link between DCs and economic sustainability performance. (b) The moderating effect of environmental dynamism on the link between DCs and environmental sustainability performance. (c) The moderating effect of environmental dynamism on the link between DCs and social sustainability performance.

bottlenecks or constraints prevent social and environmental sustainability performance to materialize in the food industry. Indeed, the use of both PLS-SEM and NCA provides a more comprehensive understanding for resolving the scientific debate on the interaction between economic, social, and environmental sustainability performance, which has been predominantly based on regression-based results only.

Subsequently, NCA was deployed to complement the PLS-SEM findings to explore whether the firm's ECOP is a necessary condition for achieving environmental (ENVP) and social performance (SOCP). The NCA followed the guidelines recommended by Dul (2021), and Dul et al. (2020) and were conducted using the latent variable scores

from the PLS-SEM analysis (Richter et al., 2020). The latent scores were imported into R software, where the analysis was performed using the NCA R package version 3.1.1 (Dul, 2021). We used effect sizes (d), p values, and bottlenecks to assess statistical significance (see Table 7).

The result (Table 7) shows that the effect size (0.276) of the necessary condition of ECOP on social performance (SOCP) is moderate and significant at $p \leq .01$. This means that ECOP is a necessary condition for a firm to achieve social performance. Thus, this supports our second hypothesis (H2) that the high ECOP of a firm is a necessity for an increase in social performance. Interestingly, the result shows that the effect size (0.089) of the necessary condition of

TABLE 7 The significance analysis and bottleneck

SOCP/ENVP	Effect size	Bottleneck										
		0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90	100
ECOP ^{SOC}	0.285***	NN	NN	NN	NN	NN	NN	50	50	63.1	91.4	100
ECOP ^{ENVP}	0.089 ^{ns}	NN	NN	NN	NN	NN	NN	NN	NN	NN	50	73.8

Note: The effect size is based on the ceiling envelopment-free disposal hull ceiling (ce-fdh). Significance testing was performed with 10,000 permutations (***)significant at $p \leq .01$, ns not significant at $p \leq .05$.

FIGURE 3 Ceiling line and bottlenecks.

ECOP on environmental performance (ENVP) is small and not significant at $p \geq .05$. This means that ECOP is not a necessary condition for a firm to achieve ENVP. Thus, our third hypothesis (H3) is not supported. In other words, the high ECOP of a firm is not a necessity for an increase in ENVP. This suggests that although ECOP is sufficient (as supported by the regression-based analysis in Section 4.2), other factors such as regulations and stakeholder requirements are more necessary to achieve ENVP. Further conditional analysis was assessed using bottleneck scores. The results show that ECOP must be present to achieve at least 60% of social performance. This means that to achieve a level of social performance beyond 60%, ECOP must be higher than 50%.

The NCA plots in Figure 3 illustrate the results from the bottleneck analysis shown in Table 7. The ceiling line (i.e., CE-FDH) in both Figure 3a,b separates the areas with and without observations. According to Hauff et al. (2019), the size of the empty ceiling zone provides empirical evidence of the constraints that the determinant exerts on the outcome. A larger empty ceiling zone, as shown in Figure 3a, indicates that economic sustainability performance has a stronger influence on social sustainability performance and is a necessary condition for it to occur. Conversely, a smaller empty ceiling zone in Figure 3b suggests that ECOP has less impact on ENVP and is not a necessary factor for its improvement.

5 | DISCUSSION

The debate on whether and how DCs affect sustainability performance is still not fully addressed in the existing literature (Baía & Ferreira, 2019; Siems et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2019). This study provides several contributions to theory as well as actionable insights for managers and policymakers.

5.1 | Theoretical implication

The main contributions of this study to theory are fourfold.

First, this study provides important empirical evidence of the effectiveness of DCs on the ECOP, SOP, and ENVP of the fishing industry. Although the fishing industry is dominated by small and medium-sized enterprises, DCs appear to be important for improving its sustainability performance. In contrast to previous studies (Schilke et al., 2018; Wu, 2010), that assumed that DCs are useful for large firms, this study provides evidence that possessing DCs is necessary to improve sustainability performance regardless of FSIZE.

Second, despite recent efforts to examine the relationship between DCs and sustainability performance (e.g., Kumar et al., 2018; Shang et al., 2019), there has been limited attention to the impact of

these capabilities at varying levels of EnvD. Previous studies have focused on the mediation of this relationship, such as in the case of resource management capabilities (Shang et al., 2019). but the path-dependence of this relationship remains a matter of theoretical assertion. This study expands the current knowledge by providing empirical evidence supporting a path-dependent relationship between DCs and sustainability performance. The results of this study indicate that the effectiveness of DCs on sustainability performance is context-dependent and varies with different degrees of EnvD. It is important to understand the impact of DCs on sustainability performance in different degrees of EnvD as it can help firms strategically align their deployment of these capabilities to maximize benefits and minimize costs. Interestingly, this study found that the effect of DCs on social sustainability performance was not dependent on EnvD. This suggests that EnvD, as reflected in regulatory dynamics and market dynamics, does not affect social performance as the laws and regulations governing worker diversity, labor, and community health seem to be constant regardless of the degree of EnvD in the industry.

Third, this study differs from previous studies by investigating the impact of DCs on ENVP in the context of varying levels of EnvD. Instead of relying on higher-order constructs, such as sense, seize, and transformation (e.g., Shang et al., 2019; Wilden et al., 2013), this study uses lower-order constructs to capture the true essence of DCs development. The lower-order constructs encompass abilities, strategic routines (e.g., knowledge development), processes (e.g., organizational responsiveness), and best practices (e.g., sustainability control mechanisms). This approach provides a more nuanced understanding of the role of DCs on sustainability performance, especially in a rapidly changing environment. Thus, this study expands knowledge of the ongoing scholarly debate on the conceptualization of DCs.

Fourth, this study expands the current knowledge to the scholarly debate on the interaction of three bottom line of sustainability by using necessary logic reasoning rather than sufficient or configuration reasoning. Previous studies (e.g., Jyoti & Khanna, 2021; Sudusinghe & Seuring, 2020; Zhou et al., 2019), have made efforts to contribute to the interaction between the three bottom lines of sustainability. However, this study uses a NCA to provide further evidence for the scientific debate. Thus, this is among the first studies to use NCA to build an argument why economically sustainable firms are more likely to improve social performance but not ENVP. Since the result shows that the firms need ECOP to improve their social performance, it is consistent with practitioners' understanding that firms that make profits increase their ability to contribute to society much more than when they do not make profits. Our result is exemplified by the ramification of COVID-19 on sustainability performance. For instance, it was evident that most firms failed to create a decent work environment and reduced the number of employees, while other workers were forced to accept wage cuts. We can fairly conclude that ECOP is a necessary condition for social performance. On the other hand, because the context of this study is inherently more focused on natural resource conservation (i.e., fish stocks and seabed management), ECOP is only a sufficient condition for ENVP, not a necessary one. This result is consistent with Sarkis (2020)'s findings that despite the

slowdown in firm profitability growth during the crisis, there was still an improvement in ENVP, such as a decrease in GHG emissions. Nevertheless, despite the author's intriguing findings but they lacked empirical evidence to generalize the results. In this regard, using empirical evidence we argue that causality between the three bottom lines of sustainability could also be influenced by industry context and changing environment. Since we used a novelty method for analysis (i.e., NCA), we can add to the existing scientific debate that ECOP is not only a sufficient condition for achieving social performance but also a necessary one. On the other hand, ECOP is a sufficient but not necessary condition for achieving ENVP, especially for those industries that focus more on natural resource conservation.

5.2 | Managerial implications

For managers, the results of our study provide evidence that DCs enhance any triple bottom line of sustainability, especially in a rapidly changing environment. Interestingly, our results show that ECOP is a necessary condition for social performance. Since most of our data come from small to mid-sized firms (97%), we recommend that managers of small firms prioritize ECOP while improving SOP and ENVP. In this way, the future financial stability of their firms will not be jeopardized. Since our results show that ECOP is not a necessary condition for ENVP, we recommend that managers adhere to environmental policies and regulations that govern environmental sustainability practices. In this regard, the government and other policy makers should continue to monitor firms' compliance with environmental regulations and establish a subsidized environmental practices project that encourages voluntary participation by all major players in the food industry. Moreover, this study highlights the degree of EnvD that managers should consider when deciding on the type of capabilities (dynamic vs. ordinal capabilities) they should employ to achieve superior sustainability performance. This will help managers to deploy relevant capabilities to achieve sustainability performance and thus minimize the associated development costs.

6 | CONCLUSION

Overall, this study provides valuable insights into the role of DCs in driving sustainability performance in a rapidly changing environment upon the condition of EnvD. This study commenced with the premise that the development of DCs is essential for firms operating in a rapidly changing environment to improve their ECOP, SOP, and ENVP. This is because firms possessing DCs are more likely to exhibit innovative behavior and increased responsiveness in addressing sustainability issues in an ever-evolving environment.

Eight hypotheses were therefore developed and tested using data from the Norwegian fishing industry, with the results confirming a positive relationship between DCs and firms' ECOP, SOP, and ENVP. Additionally, the study examined the moderating effects of EnvD on the relationship between DCs and sustainability performance. The

results demonstrate that DCs have a significantly positive impact on economic and environmental sustainability performance when a firm is faced with increasing EnvD. However, no statistically significant moderation effect was observed in the relationship between DCs and social sustainability. Furthermore, the results of the conditional analysis indicated that ECOP is a necessary condition for enhancing social performance, but not ENVP.

Nevertheless, despite the intriguing results of this study, it is important to note some limitations that offer potential avenues for future research. First, the results of this study are based on cross-sectional data, suggesting the need for further longitudinal studies to examine the use of DCs and how they change over time. Second, as our results show that the relationship between DCs and sustainability performance is context-dependent, it would be useful to replicate this study by analyzing data from multiple industries. This could provide a better understanding of the moderating effects of industry context on the relationship between DCs and sustainability performance. Third, this study only collected data from a single industry (i.e., the fishing industry), which limits its generalizability, especially in food sectors (e.g., agricultural products). Further studies could be conducted by collecting data from other primary food industries for results comparison. Fourth, it would be valuable to explore further linkages between the triple bottom line of sustainability in industries that do not focus on natural resource conservation to determine which dimension is a necessary condition for another dimension. This is to confirm our conclusion that the interaction between the three dimensions is highly dependent on the industry context.

Lastly, while this study employed a comprehensive and diverse set of measurement items in operationalizing constructs relevant to the fishing context, it may still be limited by the omission of other factors that contribute to negative environmental consequences. These factors include the types of fishing gear used, the location of fishing activities, and the methods used to dispose of fishing waste. These omissions can result in an incomplete understanding of the effectiveness of DCs in enhancing ENVP. To address this limitation, future research may use mixed research methods (e.g., case study and survey) or use multiple key informants to get more insights into other measurement variables.

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ENDNOTE

¹ NOFIMA is the Norwegian food research institute that conducts research and development for aquaculture, fishing, and food industries <https://nofima.com/about/>

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APPENDIX A: COMPUTATION OF RELIABILITY OF HIGHER-ORDER CONSTRUCTS (HOCs)

A.1 | AVE for HOCs

$$AVE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^M l_i^2}{M}, \tag{1}$$

where, l_i and M represent loadings of the LOCs of specific HOCs and M LOCs ($i = 1, \dots, M$). The loadings are shown in Figure 1. Using formula (1) above, the AVE for DCs is 0.582 (0.7152 + 0.7852

+ 0.7872)/3. Similarly, the AVE for EnvD is 0.698 (0.7712 + 0.8952)/2.

A.2 | Composite reliability (ρ_c) for HOCs

$$\text{Composite reliability } (\rho_c) = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^M l_i)^2}{(\sum_{i=1}^M l_i)^2 + \sum_{i=1}^M \text{var}(e_i)} \tag{2}$$

Here, e_i stands for measurement error of the LOCs i , and $\text{var}(e_i)$ represents measurement error variance which is computed as $1-l_i^2$. Therefore, composite reliability of two HOCs are computed as follows,

$$\text{DCs' } (\rho_c) = \frac{(0.715+0.785+0.787)^2}{(0.715+0.785+0.787)^2+(1-0.715)^2+(1-0.785)^2+(1-0.787)^2} = 0.807.$$

$$\text{EnvD } (\rho_c) = \frac{(0.771+0.895)^2}{(0.771+0.895)^2+(1-0.771)^2+(1-0.895)^2} = 0.821.$$

A.3 | Cronbach's alpha for HOCs

$$\text{Cronbach's alpha} = \frac{M \cdot \bar{r}}{1 + (M - 1) \cdot \bar{r}} \tag{3}$$

Here, \bar{r} represents mean correlation between LOCs. In this study the HOCs had three LOCs in each (i.e., $M = 3$), and average correlations between LOCs scores are 0.378 and 0.405 for DCs and EnvD respectively as shown below.

Correlations between LOCs of DCs and EnvD.
Therefore,

	KND	REFC	ORGR	MKTD	REGD
KND	1			MKTD	1
REFC	0.400	1		REGD	0.405
ORGR	0.361	0.372	1		
Average	0.378			Average	0.405

$$\text{DCs Cronbach's alpha} = \frac{3 \times 0.378}{1 + (3 - 1) \cdot 0.378} = 0.645.$$

$$\text{EnvD Cronbach's alpha} = \frac{2 \times 0.405}{1 + (2 - 1) \cdot 0.405} = 0.577.$$